

Well-tailored words: Comparing the fit of articles within scholarly journals to their citation rates

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The articles published within a scholarly journal reflect the research interests and activities of the community of authors contributing to it; it is not only the underlying ideas that may be shared, but the language used to express them. This work-in-progress uses the text of articles' abstracts to attempt to further understand the relationship between scholarly articles and the journals in which they are published, and, through these, the communities and disciplines in which research takes place. An indicator of journal fit, leveraging cosine similarity, is used to characterize the positioning of articles within seventy-five journals across three subject areas, and is compared to the articles' citation impact. A weak but significant correlation is found between the two, and differing distributions of fit across journals is observed.

1. Introduction

Scholarly journals, beyond simply being a venue for publication, are a key element in the development of disciplines with their own, more or less differentiated, epistemic cultures (Gingras, 2013; Knorr Cetina, 1991). Becoming socialized to a scholarly community and progressing one's academic career thus involves gaining an understanding of these norms and practices, and adopting the methods and language of the community (Hagstrom, 1975).

Because researchers consider their research's fit to the journal as one of the main criteria for selecting a publishing venue (Rowley et al., 2022; Solomon & Björk, 2012; Tenopir et al., 2016), often outweighing even the importance of citation impact (Coonin & Younce, 2010), they might adapt their writing accordingly by adopting the style and vocabulary of past research published in their target journal. This process further normalizes the language of scholarly communities (Wakeling et al., 2019).

The fit of the manuscript with the journal is not only relevant for the authors but also (if not more so) for the journal editors and reviewers, the latter often being asked to assess the relevance of a paper for the journal's readership as part of the review process. Such mechanisms plausibly contribute to the inclusion within a journal of papers that discuss similar topics, use similar methods, and are written in similar language. Textual similarity may also speak to a journal's place within its discipline as a whole, as the language used by its community shifts, either independently or in relation to other disciplines (Bérubé et al., 2018; Dias et al., 2018).

2. Purpose

While an article's journal fit presumably plays a role in publishing decisions by authors, reviewers, and editors, little is known about how this fit to the publishing journal relates to the

citation impact of specific publications. If, indeed, being published alongside other similar papers improves the discoverability or perceived relevance of a work, we might expect a positive relationship to exist; contrarily, less-similar works may have an advantage in visibility through differentiation or perceived novelty. This work-in-progress, building on work by Mongeon et al. (2019), explores the relationship between journal fit (indicated by the lexical similarity of a manuscript and others published in the same journal) and citation impact.

3. Data and Methods

Data collection and processing, as well as journal fit calculations, correlation measurement, and visualizations were performed using custom R code.

3.1. Data Source and Collection

We retrieved the top 25 journals listed in Scopus, based on CiteScore (James et al., 2019), in three subject areas: Library & Information Science, Geology, and Clinical Psychology. The journals selected were those with the highest CiteScore whose highest percentile was within the selected subject area for the year 2019, and which had a minimum of 100 articles. Journals were then matched to their OpenAlex source IDs (Priem et al., 2022), and metadata records for works published in these journals during the 2015-2019 period were retrieved using the `openalexR` package (Aria & Le, 2023). This period was selected to allow for sufficient citations to accrue to articles.

Table 1. Raw and filtered articles by subject area

Subject Area	Works Retrieved	Filtered Articles
Clinical Psychology	20,579	17,964
Geology	25,308	23,307
Library and Information Sciences	13,088	11,682
<i>Random sample</i>	<i>10,000</i>	<i>6,978</i>

Additionally, 10,000 random English-language articles were retrieved for the same time period, and were assigned to one of 10 random “journals”, as a baseline. Table 1 shows the number of works retrieved in each area, as well as the remaining articles after filtering the dataset.

3.2. Data Preparation

Works in all three subject areas were filtered to include only those that were marked as type “article”, were neither retracted nor identified as para-textual, and whose metadata records were indicated as being in English. In all cases, this was determined using the OpenAlex metadata fields. Works were also discarded if their titles consisted of fewer than five characters or their abstracts fewer than 100 characters. The remaining fields of interest after filtering works are *id*, *display_name* (title), *ab* (abstract text), *so_id* (source ID of the journal), *publication_year*, and *cited_by_count*.

For the remaining works, text tokens were produced by joining the titles to the abstracts, replacing all non-alphabetic characters with spaces, and calling R’s `unnest_tokens()` function, which also automatically converts to lower-case. Stopwords, that is the most common English-language terms, were filtered out, and remaining terms were stemmed.

3.3. Determining Journal Fit

An article’s fit to a journal is operationalized here as the average cosine similarity between the terms in a paper’s title and abstract, and all others published in the journal within the same time

period. Mongeon et al. (2019) proposed a similar approach for measuring the scope of journals using trigrams, and similarities calculated in this manner have been found to reflect more strongly-related publications (Sainte-Marie et al., 2020). Cosine similarity is calculated using the frequencies of the term tokens in each document.

$$S_{A,B} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i B_i}{\sqrt{(\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2)(\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2)}}$$

Similarities fall between a range of 0, meaning no two terms are shared between two works, and 1, meaning that two works share identical distributions of terms. After calculating the similarity between each pair of articles in a journal, J , we take the mean similarity between each article and the others (excluding itself).

$$F_A = \frac{\sum_{B \in J} S_{A,B}}{|J| - 1}$$

A higher F value would indicate a greater average similarity between an article and the others published in the same journal over a set time period, indicating a greater fit to that journal.

3.4. Correlation to Citations

To understand the relationship between an article’s journal fit and its impact, we perform a Spearman rank correlation between the article’s journal fit, as calculated above, and citation count. To ensure valid comparisons over time, as well as between journals, citation counts are normalized by first calculating the mean citation count for a journal’s articles in a given year, then dividing each article’s citations by the average for its journal and year. Correlations are then calculated for each individual journal, and across each subject area as a whole.

4. Results

4.1. Distribution of Journal Fit

After calculating the cosine similarities between each article in the selected journals, and determining the articles’ journal fit by taking the average, we can observe the distribution of journal fit at the level of both the individual journal and the overall discipline. Table 2 shows descriptive statistics for fit at the level of the subject area, as well as the baseline fit for our randomly-assigned “journals”.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of journal fit by subject area

Subject Area	Articles	Min. Fit	Median Fit	Mean Fit	Max. Fit	SD
Clinical Psych.	17,964	0.006	0.112	0.116	0.495	0.041
Geology	23,307	0.005	0.101	0.112	0.286	0.051
LIS	11,682	0.001	0.105	0.110	0.309	0.042
<i>Random sample</i>	<i>6,978</i>	<i>0.001</i>	<i>0.027</i>	<i>0.028</i>	<i>0.065</i>	<i>0.010</i>

The mean, median, and maximum fit values in each of the three selected subject areas are considerably higher than the baselines established by the random sample. As seen in Figure 1, all three subject areas are right-skewed. While all three have a similar average fit, the length of the tail representing better-fitting articles differs, particularly in the area of Clinical Psychology.

Figure 1. Distribution of articles by journal fit within subject areas

Table 3 shows statistics for fit at the journal level for the top five journals, by the number of articles, in each of the selected subject areas. Note that some journals, particularly in the LIS category, may have issues with classification (e.g., *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*).

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of fit for top five journals (by article count) per area

Subj. area	Journal	Articles	Min Fit	Mean Fit	Med Fit	Max Fit	SD
Clinical Psych.	J. of Affective Disorders	4,120	0.015	0.122	0.121	0.224	0.035
	Journal of Alzheimer's Disease	3,479	0.016	0.121	0.121	0.222	0.034
	Addictive Behaviors	1,750	0.015	0.089	0.089	0.154	0.023
	Psychological Assessment	760	0.059	0.128	0.128	0.216	0.030
	Comprehensive Psychiatry	746	0.028	0.099	0.100	0.185	0.025
Geology	Remote Sensing of Environment	2,213	0.029	0.106	0.106	0.185	0.024
	Applied Clay Science	2,067	0.024	0.077	0.077	0.141	0.020
	J. of Asian Earth Sciences	1,917	0.013	0.085	0.082	0.157	0.026
	Chemical Geology	1,870	0.016	0.081	0.079	0.149	0.021
	Ore Geology Reviews	1,868	0.014	0.164	0.167	0.285	0.049
LIS	IEEE Transactions on Info. Theory	2,386	0.007	0.104	0.101	0.237	0.040
	J. of Chemical Info. and Modeling	1,659	0.013	0.097	0.097	0.190	0.026
	J. of the Assoc. for Information Science and Technology	913	0.021	0.082	0.081	0.149	0.023
	J. of Academic Librarianship	564	0.016	0.135	0.138	0.238	0.050
	International J. of Information Management	564	0.019	0.093	0.095	0.170	0.023

There is more variation in the average fit between journals than there is in the average fit at the disciplinary level; at the same time, the standard deviations at the journal level tend to be lower. Distributions of journal fit also vary at the individual journal levels, even within subject areas, as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Fit distribution in top 5 journals per subject area

4.2. Fit-Citation Correlations

Citation counts and practices differ across disciplines and journals, requiring normalization to effectively compare them (Schubert & Braun, 1986). After dividing each article's citation count by the average received by articles in the same journal during the same year, we can plot this against the article's journal fit (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Scatter plots of articles' normalized citations and journal fit

The results suggest that the more-cited articles are largely concentrated near the median score, alongside most of the other articles. A strong linear correlation appears unlikely based simply upon visual analysis. Calculating the Spearman rank correlation between normalized citations and journal fit, as seen in Table 4, confirms this.

Table 4. Spearman correlations between journal fit and citations

Subj. area	Journal	Articles	Citations	Cit./Article	Med. Fit	Correlation	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Overall</i>		52,953	1,762,825	33.3	0.106	0.100	< 0.00000001
Clinical Psychology		17,964	645,967	36.0	0.112	0.102	< 0.00000001
	Addictive Behaviors	1,750	47,230	27.0	0.089	-0.044	0.0658
	Comprehensive Psychiatry	746	19,886	26.7	0.100	0.040	0.271
	J. of Affective Disorders	4,120	155,477	37.7	0.121	0.148	< 0.00000001
	J. of Alzheimer's Disease	3,479	113,418	32.6	0.121	0.138	< 0.00000001
	Psychological Assessment	760	29,691	39.1	0.128	0.148	0.0000428
Geology		23,307	767,235	32.9	0.101	0.109	< 0.00000001
	Applied Clay Science	2,067	68,587	33.2	0.077	0.164	< 0.00000001
	Chemical Geology	1,870	53,730	28.7	0.079	0.094	0.0000507
	J. of Asian Earth Sciences	1,917	44,053	23.0	0.082	0.249	< 0.00000001
	Ore Geology Reviews	1,868	52,374	28.0	0.167	0.027	0.250
	Remote Sensing of Environment	2,213	171,464	77.5	0.106	0.183	< 0.00000001
Library & Information Sciences		11,682	349,623	29.9	0.105	0.097	< 0.00000001
	IEEE Transactions on Information Theory	2,386	66,791	28.0	0.101	0.010	0.625
	International J. of Information Management	564	52,766	93.6	0.095	0.222	0.00000009
	J. of Academic Librarianship	564	6,161	10.9	0.138	0.251	< 0.00000001
	J. of Chemical Information and Modeling	1,659	58,026	35.0	0.097	0.121	0.00000007
	J. of the Assoc. for Information Science and Technology	913	21,805	23.9	0.081	-0.091	0.00603

Correlations at the overall and subject area levels are all around 0.1. Individual journals show slightly higher correlations, in some cases, though others are even lower. Several of the individual journals' results are also not significant.

5. Discussion

5.1. General Discussion

The average journal fit for articles all three subject areas is approximately 0.1, nearly four times that of a random sampling of unrelated works, suggesting that some similarity is indeed being detected, beyond simply the shared English-language text and scholarly mode of writing. Similarly, the wider range and higher variance in fit for works within discipline-specific journals would seem to indicate the capturing of more complex interrelationships between the articles published in any given journal than would be found in a random selection of works.

Distributions of journal fit within individual journals are more varied than those encountered over entire subject areas. Different averages, ranges, and skewness were all observed, even

within the small subset of journals examined here, and these differences are prevalent within each of the subject areas being examined.

Outliers may be the result of journal-specific characteristics: articles with a fit higher than 0.3 in the Clinical Psychology category, for instance, largely belong to a single journal with only 77 articles in the dataset. LIS works with fit less than 0.1 are all from *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, and seem to contain significant amounts of mathematical notation or non-English text in their abstracts. Editorial works that failed to be filtered out using the “paratext” flag are also prominent in the high and low ends of the fit distributions. Introductions, retrospectives, and calls-for-papers tend to have high fit scores, while errata, book reviews, and obituaries are notable on the low end.

An article’s journal fit tends to have a weakly positive, but statistically significant, correlation to normalized citations. This holds at the overall and disciplinary-specific levels; individual journals show slightly stronger correlations. The weakest correlations, including some negative ones, are also the least statistically significant.

To the degree that there are patterns in the relationship between normalized citation counts (by year and journal) and journal fit, these appear to be non-linear. At the disciplinary level, more highly-cited articles within journals are loosely clustered near the median journal fit. This may be attributed to the higher overall volume of data points in this range, and the relative scarcity of highly-cited articles, but it may also be an indication of author preferences, disciplinary norms, or underlying patterns in the language used in scholarly writing. Articles with high journal fit may reflect commonly-held knowledge or be insufficiently interesting to lead to more citations than similar articles; those with low journal fit may not be relevant to other authors in the discipline, may represent a shift in topic or style that has not yet gained sufficient traction to lead to citations, or may simply be incomprehensible to readers.

5.2. Limitations

This work examines only a small subset of journals in a handful of disciplines, over a specific time period. Patterns found here may not generalize to other areas of research, or even to the examined disciplines as a whole. We limited ourselves to articles with abstract text (stored as inverted indices) available in OpenAlex, and are dependent on the quality of metadata within the OpenAlex records. The article metadata (specifically title and abstract) used in this study is limited to those records marked as being in English, but this does not necessarily indicate the original article’s language of publication, nor is it guaranteed to be entirely accurate, as this is algorithmically determined (*Work Object*, 2024). The journal fit of an article as a whole may differ from that of its abstract.

6. Conclusion

This work-in-progress used average cosine similarity of scholarly articles’ abstract text to determine their fit within the journals in which they were published, and explored the relationship between journal fit and citations for 75 journals in three different disciplines. As an indicator of journal fit, this approach successfully identifies a level of similarity in works published together, as well as differences in the degree and distribution of fit across different journals. Weak correlations were found between the journal fit of articles and their normalized citation counts, at both the overall and disciplinary levels. Slightly stronger correlations were found in some journals, with varying levels of significance.

Further development of this work will consider a broader range of disciplines and journals. We will also consider other factors that may influence the citation impact of articles (e.g., team size, authors' reputation, Journal Impact Factor, and time period) to better isolate the possible effect of journal fit on citations. Other measures to quantify this relationship, such as the distance correlation developed by Székely et al. (2007), may be investigated.

The digital era has brought changes in the ways scholars discover, access, and interact with literature. With the decline of personal subscriptions and physical journals, and the rise of search engines and databases, the use of any given article in the research process would seem to have become decoupled from its position in a journal. Likewise, the rise of open access mega-journals and a push for new publishing models centered on the use of repositories raise broader questions for the role of journals in scholarly publishing. Our results do not offer a definitive answer to the question of what the future of the journal may be, but it is hoped that our work can eventually contribute to a better understanding of the role that scholarly journals play for structuring and disseminating scholarship.

Open science practices

Article metadata used to complete this study was obtained from OpenAlex (<https://openalex.org>) and is freely available under a Creative Commons CC0 license. Processed data will be made available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13946029>.

Author contributions

Geoff Krause: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Investigation, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing
Rebecca Marjoram: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing
Philippe Mongeon: Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing financial or non-financial interests.

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